

Syntheses, characterization and biological activities of two carbamate pesticides

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Two carbamate pesticides namely *S*-ethyl-*N*-[(methylcarbamoyl)oxy]thioacetimidate (a) ($\text{CH}_3\text{-C}(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_5)=\text{NOCONHCH}_3$) and *N*-phenyl-(ethylcarbamoyl)propyl carbamate (b) [$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH-COO-CH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{-CO-NH}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)$] were synthesized in the laboratory. With the help of elemental analysis, IR and NMR spectra their structures were elucidated. The biological studies showed that *S*-ethyl-*N*-[(methylcarbamoyl)oxy]thioacetimidate (a) acts as insecticide against insects causing damages to potato, tomato, cabbage plants, while *N*-phenyl-(ethylcarbamoyl)propyl carbamate (b) has herbicidal character and can be used for cabbage and legume family crops. For estimation of the toxicity of these pesticides LC_{50} and LD_{50} were determined. The results revealed that for fish and rats compound (a) was more toxic than compound (b).

As organochlorine compounds were highly persistent and so strongly dissolved into animal fat, that they get concentrated as they moved upto the food chain causing damaging effects, were banned; therefore, broad spectrum biodegradable short lived chemical compounds such as organophosphates, carbamates and pyrethroids were developed¹⁻⁵. Carbamate pesticides are mainly used in agriculture as insecticides, fungicides, herbicides, nematocides. They are also used as biocides for industrial purposes. Carbamate-pesticides are also effective against those pests which are resistant to organochlorine and organophosphates.

Oxamyl, a product of E.I. DuPont de Nemours & Co Inc., Wilmington, Delaware, is a broad spectrum insecticide-nematicide with excellent biological efficacy on a variety of crops. To compare efficacy of oxamyl it was considered worthwhile to synthesize following two new carbamate pesticides (1) compound (a) *S*-ethyl-*N*-[(methylcarbamoyl)oxy]thioacetimidate, (2) compound (b) *N*-phenyl-(ethylcarbamoyl)propyl carbamate and study their physical, chemical and biological properties.

Results and discussion

The physical properties of synthesized compounds **a** and **b**, determined by usual methods, are given in Table I. Their structure were confirmed by element analysis, IR and NMR spectra. For compound **a**, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ experimental analysis gave : C, 41.02 (41.91); H, 6.80 (6.82); N, 15.76 (15.91); O, 18.04 (18.18); S, 18.38 (18.18) (calculated values are given in parentheses) ν_{max} (KBr) 3310 (NH), 2900 (C-H), 1710 (C=N), 1665 (>C=O), 1385 (C-N), 700 cm^{-1} (C-S); δ (CDCl_3) 11.85 (1H, s, NH-C=O), 0.95 (3H, t, CH_3), 5.35

Table I. Physical properties of *S*-ethyl-*N*-[(methylcarbamoyl)oxy]thioacetimidate (a) and *N*-phenyl-(ethylcarbamoyl)propyl carbamate (b)

	Pesticide a	Pesticide b
Physical state	Crystalline	Solid
Colour	White	Colourless
Odour	Sulphurous	Odourless
M.p.(°C)	80°	126°
Vapour pressure	0.73 mpa (25°)	Negligible
Molecular weight	176	250
Molecular formula	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$
Density	1.296 kg dm^{-3}	1.362 kg dm^{-3}
Solubility :		
Water	58 g dm^{-3}	3.7 g dm^{-3}
Methanol	1000 g dm^{-3}	1400 g dm^{-3}
Acetone	700 g dm^{-3}	830 g dm^{-3}
Toluene	28 g dm^{-3}	-
Ethanol	400 g dm^{-3}	720 g dm^{-3}
Diethyl formamide	-	1360 g dm^{-3}

(2H, q, CH_2CH_3), 2.30 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3). For compound **b**, $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ experimental value were : C, 62.12 (62.4); H, 7.36 (7.2); N, 11.42 (11.2); O, 19.10 (19.28) (calculated values are in parentheses) ν_{max} (KBr) 3340 (NH), 3020 (C-H), 1675 (>C=O), 1600 (C-O) and 1380 cm^{-1} (C-N); δ (CDCl_3) 7.2 (5H, s, aromatic), 12.55 (1H, s, NH-COO), 11.60 (1H, s, NH-C=O), 1.60 (2H, NH- $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2$), 2.30 (3H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_3$), 0.95 (3H, t, CH_3), 4.52 (1H, t, CH).

Preliminary studies suggest that compound **a** acts as an insecticide and compound **b** as a herbicide. The result shows that on spraying 100-400 g ai ha^{-1} of compound **a** on the

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Table 2. Effect of different concentration of *S*-ethyl-*N*-[(methylcarbamoyl)oxy]thioacetimidate (**a**) on larval population of *Plutella xylostella* and herbicidal activity of *N*-phenylethylcarbamoyl propylcarbamate (**b**)

Dose g ai ha	Pesticide a			Dose g ai ha	Pesticide b			
	Population % decrease from control after (days)				Mean % of herbicidal control			
	1	7	14		Cabbage	Lettuce	Garden legume	Wheat
100	41.6	52.8	27.5	400	30	20	40	36
200	49.1	59.9	33.0	800	50	46	66	60
300	56.5	65.2	30.4	1000	80	84	94	86
400	61.1	72.2	34.3					

Table 3. Effect of different concentration of *S*-ethyl-*N*-(methylcarbamoyl)oxythioacetimidate (**a**) and *N*-phenyl-(ethylcarbamoyl)propyl carbamate (**b**) on the survival percentage of twenty five *Heteropneustes fossilis* after 96 h; and oral toxicity in twelve male albino rats according to probit analysis

Fishes						Rats									
Pesticide a			Pesticide b			Pesticide a					Pesticide b				
Concen- tration (ppm)	Survival %	LC ₅₀ ppm	Concen- tration (ppm)	Survival %	LC ₅₀ ppm	Dose mg/kg body wt.	Log dose	% mortality	Probit	LD ₅₀ mg/kg body wt.	Dose mg/kg body wt.	Log dose	% mortality	Probit	LD ₅₀ mg/kg body wt.
2	80		10	92		15	1.1761	8.33	3.631		750	2.875	8.33	3.631	
3	64		15	80		20	1.3010	33.33	4.569		1000	3.000	16.67	4.034	
4	48		20	64		30	1.4771	50.00	5.000		2000	3.301	25.00	4.294	
5	32	3.9	25	52	25.2	40	1.6021	58.33	5.211	31.7	3000	3.4771	33.33	4.569	
6	20		30	32		50	1.6990	66.67	5.431		5000	3.6990	41.67	4.790	3018
8	12		40	20		60	1.7781	75.00	5.674		7500	3.8750	66.67	5.431	
10	0		50	4		75	1.875	83.33	5.968		10000	4.000	83.33	5.968	
			60	0		100	2.000	91.66	6.383		12500	4.0969	91.66	6.383	

crop, the larval population of insect *P. xylostella* decreased 50 to 72% after seven days of application (Table 2). But after 14 days of application, the larval population increased (27–69%) from 1st day of application, indicating the degradation of compound **a**. Table 2 also denotes that with the increase in concentration from 400 to 1000 g ai ha⁻¹ of compound **b**, the herbicidal activity was increased and more effective in garden legume.

The LC₅₀ (Table 3) for fish of compound **a** was 3.9 ppm while that of compound **b** was 25.2 ppm denoting that compound **a** had more aquatic toxicity than compound **b**.

The oral LC₅₀ (Table 3) value for male rats of compound **a** was 31.7 mg kg⁻¹ body weight and compound **b** was 3018 mg kg⁻¹ body weight.

From these studies it may be inferred that compound **a** has more pesticidal activity than compound **b** but later has more stability.

Material and methods :

Synthesis route of S-ethyl-N-[(methylcarbamoyl)oxy]-thioacetimidate a :

Scheme 1 :

(in ether and pentane) (dropwise in 4 h)

- (i) 5± 3°
- (ii) kept for 3 days at 8°
- (iii) Temp. raised to 13° for one day
- (iv) Supernatant withdrawn
Replaced by equal amount of anhy. ether

S-Ethyl thioacetamide hydrochloride (75% yield)

(I)

Scheme 2 :

(Yield 55% in chloroform)

S-Ethyl-N-hydroxyacetimidate

(II)

Scheme 3 :

S-Ethyl-N-(methylcarbamoyl)oxythioacetimidate
(Pure compound a)

Synthesis route of N-phenyl(ethylcarbamoyl)propyl carbamate b :

Scheme 1 :

Scheme 2 :

Biological studies : Preliminary studies showed that compound S-ethyl-N-[(methylcarbamoyl)oxy]thioacetimidate (a) possessed insecticidal property while N-phenyl-(ethylcarbamoyl)propylcarbamate (b) showed herbicidal activity.

Studies on insecticidal activity of S-ethyl-N-(methylcarbamoyl)oxy]thioacetimidate (a) :

The field trial was laid to study insecticidal⁶ activity of compound a in five 5 m² plots. The cabbage was selected for the field trial. Four aqueous solution of compound a with concentration 100, 200, 300, 400 g ai ha⁻¹ was sprayed separately in four plots (fifth was for blank). Before day one and after 1, 7 and 14 days of spraying population counts of insect, *Plutella xylostella* were recorded. From these data mean larval population on cabbage was estimated. The data are recorded in Table 2.

Evaluation of herbicidal activity of N-phenyl(ethylcarbamoyl)propylcarbamate (b) :

For the foliar application test⁷ the aqueous solution of compound b was sprayed over the foliage of cabbage, lettuce, garden legume and wheat plants at the spray doses of 400, 800, 1000 g ai ha⁻¹ separately. Spraying was performed with the plants employed at either the two or three leaf stage. The growth inhibition of compounds was evaluated at 400, 800 and 1000 g ai ha⁻¹. Approximately three weeks after the spraying the herbicidal activity of each dose was assessed by visual observation of the treated plants in comparison with the untreated controls. According to the extent of the injury of plants herbicidal potency was assessed. Mean values are recorded in Table 2.

Determination of LC₅₀ :

To determine the LC₅₀ of synthesized compounds a and b for fish a solution of 2 to 10 ppm of compound a and 10 to 60 ppm of compound b was prepared separately in 20 L of water and stored in aquaria. Twenty five fish were transferred to each aquarium containing test solution, which was

Note

changed after 24 h to maintain the test concentration. No food was provided during the experimental period. The survival number in each concentration was recorded after 96 h. A control aquaria with equal number of fish was also maintained under similar condition. The data are recorded in Table 3.

Determination of LD₅₀ :

For determination of LD₅₀ of synthesized compounds **a** and **b**, nine sets of experiments of each compound with 12 male rats were performed separately with suitable blank. The concentration of compound **a** was from 15 mg kg⁻¹ to 100 mg kg⁻¹ body weight while of compound **b** was 750 to 12500 mg kg⁻¹ body weight (average body weight of rat was 180 ± 20 g). After 96 h of treatment the mortality number and percentage for each dose was noted. The data are given in Table 3.

Log-dose and probit mortality method⁸ was used for calculation of LD₅₀. The data are recorded in Table 3.

IR (KBr) and NMR of both the compounds **a** and **b** were also recorded.

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